

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF CHRONIC DISEASES OF THE DIGESTIVE SYSTEM IN CHILDREN

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Annotation. Recently in Uzbekistan, the number of children suffering from chronic inflammatory diseases of the digestive system has been growing in Uzbekistan. This article discusses the clinical manifestations of chronic diseases of the gastroduodenal zone in children. The urgency of the problem of chronic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract is due to the significant prevalence of diseases of the digestive system in children, among which the leading place is occupied by gastroduodenal pathology. The high prevalence of this pathology among children is an important social and medical problem. Analysis of indicators of the prevalence of diseases of the digestive system in children in the Russian Federation shows that over the past 20 years there has been a significant increase in gastroenterological pathology in children and there is an uncontrolled increase in the frequency of diseases of the stomach and duodenum. Clinical manifestations of chronic pathology of the gastroduodenal zone are diverse and depend on the degree of structural changes in the organs, their localization, the stage of the pathological process, the functional state and metabolic disorders in the body. Chronic diseases of the digestive system in children very often begin in pre-school and school age. Diseases of the gastroduodenal zone are characterized by a recurrent course, which leads to pronounced anatomical changes in the organ and further to disability and disability of the adult population.

Key words: clinical manifestations, digestive organs, chronic diseases.

Materials and methods of research. A total of 47 children aged 1-15 years with various pathologies of the gastroduodenal zone, which was mainly of a chronic combined nature, were examined [15,25]. The majority of the examined patients were children with chronic gastritis (39.7% of the total number of children), gastroduodenitis (17.5%), gallbladder dysfunction, where this diagnosis was the main one (16.2%), and chronic cholecystocholangitis (11.8%) [9, 19].

In all nosological units, except for chronic pancreatitis and cholangitis, there was a predominance of sick girls in relation to boys, this trend was especially pronounced in the case of chronic cholecystocholangitis (73.2% - girls), gallbladder dysfunction (67.5%), chronic gastritis (64.4%), duodenitis (58.3%) [16]. This generally coincides with the data [3, 10] on the greater susceptibility of girls to chronic non-infectious pathology of the gastroduodenal zone. In this study, we proceeded from the classification of chronic gastritis, gastroduodenitis, duodenitis, and peptic ulcer in children, proposed by A.V. Mazurin et al. [4,13,14,22], according to which three stages are identified in the course of these diseases: I – exacerbation, II – incomplete remission, and III – complete clinical remission. A similar classification is proposed for chronic inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract and chronic pancreatitis in children.

All the examined children with various inflammatory diseases of the gastro- duodenal zone had a clinic characteristic of the acute stage when they were admitted to the hospital- ния, and were usually prescribed for outpatient treatment in incomplete remission [20].

Техъ заболявания колебалась следуюduration of the disease varied as follows: up to one year — 11.1%, from 1 to 3 years — in 56.4%, over 3 years — in 32.5% of the total number of ционарнопатients surveyed in the hospital.

Results and their discussion. As can be seen from Table 1, 60.5% of the examined children showed aviolation of appetite, i.e. its decrease or selective- тельный appetite, in half of the children with pepticulcer disease of the stomach, duodenum, a violation of appetitewas observed in the form of its sharpincrease with rapid satiety after taking не-a small amount food. The most pronounced loss of appetitewas observed in children with chroniccholangitis, pancreatitis, холецистохо- cholecystocholangitis,cholecystitis, and duodenitis.

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